

HUMAN RIGHTS AND THE RULE OF LAW AS THE CORNERSTONE OF EFFECTIVE COUNTER-TERRORISM EFFORTS

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Abstract. In this article, the importance of human rights and rule of law in countering terrorism was analyzed.

Key words: human rights, rule of law, counter-terrorism, extremism, reintegration, civil society, international security.

Аннотация. Мазкур мақолада терроризмга қарши курашишда инсон ҳуқуқлари ва қонун устуворлигининг аҳамияти таҳлил қилинган.

Калит сўзлар: инсон ҳуқуқлари, қонун устуворлиги, терроризмга қарши кураш, экстремизм, реинтеграция, фуқаролик жамияти.

Аннотация. В статье анализируются вопросы обеспечения законности и соблюдения прав человека в борьбе с терроризмом и экстремизмом.

Ключевые слова: права человека, верховенство закона, борьба с терроризмом, экстремизмом, реинтеграция, гражданское общество, международная безопасность.

Terrorism is fundamentally the denial and destruction of human rights, as such, fighting terrorism will never be successful if the same denial and destruction continue.

The pandemic, which has affected all spheres of public life and economic activity, is having the most negative impact on the achievement of the **UN SDGs**¹. The crises in economy and social life are worsening global inequality, significantly increasing the risks of conflicts and terrorist ideas.

As the Special Rapporteur on the promotion and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms

while countering terrorism affirmed human rights and rule of law compliant capacity building play a valuable role in strengthening a **“whole-of society” approach**² to countering terrorism.

States, therefore, must ensure that measures taken to counter terrorist activity must be compliant with international human rights standards.

Fifteen years ago, all the countries of the world unanimously endorsed the **UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy**³. When all five Central Asian nations adopted the **Joint Action Plan**⁴ for its implementation in 2011, it became the first

¹ <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>.

² <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/G20/045/67/PDF/G2004567.pdf?OpenElement>.

³ <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N05/504/88/PDF/N0550488.pdf?OpenElement>.

⁴ <https://unrcca.unmissions.org/joint-plan-action>.

effective example for the regionalization of this policy document.

I would like to mention the success of the international conference “**Regional Cooperation in Central Asia in the Framework of the Joint Action Plan for the Implementation of the UN Global 8 Counter-Terrorism Strategy**”, which was held 2 months ago in Tashkent (March 3-4, 2022).

UN Secretary General António Guterres stressed that the Tashkent Conference demonstrates the political will of the Central Asian states to work together to prevent and combat the threat of terrorism⁵. Regular Consultative Meetings of the Heads of Central Asian States help to realize Uzbekistan’s potential in guaranteeing regional security and long-term development.

Uzbekistan’s state policy in this area is based on a comprehensive, inclusive and consistent approach which combines the use of preventive measures along with law enforcement, and not only state bodies, but also civil society institutions actively participate in this process.

The fundamental basis for combating terrorism in Uzbekistan is to ensure human rights and freedoms and the rule of law. We are convinced that combating terrorism and protecting human rights are not conflicting goals, but complementary and mutually reinforcing.

Last January Uzbek Government adopted “**New Development Strategy for the next five years**”⁶ the goal of which is “**Formation of effective mechanisms to combat extremism and terrorism**”. Repatriation and reintegration of women and children from conflict zones is another important Uzbek policy.

At the forty-seventh regular session of the Human Rights Council: The Government of Uzbekistan with the Special Rapporteur was organized **Side event on the reintegration of women and children**⁷ previously detained in camps in North-East Syria.

During last 3 years, under **special operation “Mehr-Mercy”** more than **530** citizens have been

returned from the armed conflict zones (Syria, Iraq, Afghanistan) to their motherland. More than 370 children have been provided with opportunity to integrate into normal life.

Uzbekistan proposed the formation of a **Regional Expert Council under the auspices of the UNOCT** to develop proposals for combating terrorist propaganda in Central Asian countries.

Uzbek Government agrees with the UN Global Counter-Terrorism Strategy and the Special Rapporteur’s position that the terrorism poses a serious challenge to the very tenets of the rule of law, protection of human rights and their effective implementation.

Nobel Prize winner **Malala Yousafzai** rightly said, “With guns you can kill terrorists, with education you can kill terrorism.”

Let us not forget, investing in the prevention of violent extremism costs far less than mitigating its consequences. Prevention is not only better than cure – it is also cheaper!

First. Preventing violent extremism is first and foremost a national challenge, and also a local undertaking in Uzbekistan. A culture of dialogue, inclusive solutions and respect for all nationalities constitute the foundation for peace.

Second. We are focusing on youth, through programs to prevent violence at home, at school and in public places, and programs to teach young people about the risks of using digital media.

Third. Uzbekistan is also developing a National Action Plan for the implementation of recommendations of **UN Resolution 1325 “Women, Peace, and Security”**⁸.

Fourth. The promotion and protection of human rights while combating terrorism is also reflected in Uzbekistan’s **National Strategy against Extremism and Terrorism**⁹ which includes issues of protecting women’s rights, broad involvement of civil society institutions and the media as well as improving the legislation to implement international standards.

⁵ https://www.un.org/counterterrorism/sites/www.un.org.counterterrorism/files/20220304_press_release_closing_tashkent_conference_eng_final.pdf.

⁶ <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-5841063>.

⁷ <https://uzbekistan.un.org/en/163958-uzbekistan-un-expert-applauds-return-women-and-children-conflict-zones-recommends-further>.

⁸ <https://documents-dds-ny.un.org/doc/UNDOC/GEN/N00/720/18/PDF/N0072018.pdf?OpenElement>.

⁹ <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5491626>.

Last December, the Special Rapporteur on promotion and protection of human rights and fundamental freedoms while countering terrorism, **Fionnuala Ni Aoláin** visited Uzbekistan.

Uzbekistan welcomes the Final Report from the Special Rapporteur and expresses its gratitude for constructive proposals and recommendations. The preliminary National Action Plan is now being developed with broad civil society input.

Today, in many parts of the world, we observe an increase in interconfessional and inter-ethnic contradictions and hatred. Uzbekistan initiated a special UN General Assembly Resolution on “Education and Religious Tolerance”¹⁰ two years ago.

In 2023, Uzbekistan will host a high-level conference on “**Enlightenment and Religious Tolerance**”. The conference will provide an opportunity to discuss consensus approaches and effective methods to combat radicalization, promote prosperity, and maintain stability in society.

Uzbekistan is also initiating a number of effective cooperation mechanisms on developing global counter-terrorism potential.

First. The most important condition for successfully countering extremism and terrorism is

an effective youth policy. We also initiated to convene in 2023 in Samarkand **Youth Council of the Central and South Asia, as well as to promote to the adoption of UN Convention on Youth Rights.**

Second. To strengthen the mechanisms for monitoring of the implementation of the JPoA, coordination of interaction between the Central Asian countries, Uzbekistan advocated the opening of the **UN Counter-Terrorism Office in our region.**

Third. Uzbekistan initiated the creation of the Central Asian unified **electronic network on cyberterrorism** within the Program on Cybersecurity and New Technologies.

Fourth. We are ready to implement **E-learning course on the protection of human rights and the rule of law in the context of counter-terrorism in Central Asia**¹¹, as well as to translate it into the national language.

International experience has shown, if we destroy human rights and rule of law in the response to terrorism, they will win.

We believe that as long as all members of the international community join hands and gather more strength, we will be able to defeat terrorism and safeguard international and regional peace and security.

¹⁰ <https://cabar.asia/en/uzbekistan-towards-religious-freedom>.

¹¹ <https://unrcca.unmissions.org/unrcca-launches-e-learning-course-human-rights-and-counter-terrorism-central-asia>.